

Morphological, Nutritional and Some Behavioral Characteristics of Common Palm Civet (*Paradoxurus hermaphroditus*) in Captivity

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Abstract:

This paper presents the results of monitoring the morphological characteristics and some behavioral habits of the common palm civet (*Paradoxurus hermaphroditus*) in captivity. In terms of morphology, the civet in captivity also has the typical characteristics of the species as in the wild. The fur is moldy gray or moldy brown, the fur tips are black; along the back, the flanks have dark brown spots or often form three stripes running along the back from the shoulder to the base of the ear. The tail has unclear or black streaks at the base of the tail, the tail tip is usually black, however in some individuals it can be white; the nose, cheeks, ears, lower thighs and four hooves

are black; the belly is gray. When the civet is young, the black brown spots are not clear, the fur is rough. As it gets older, the fur becomes smoother and the dark brown spots become clearer. In captivity, the main activities of the civet are moving, eating and resting. The civet is mainly active at night (daytime 233.16 minutes, accounting for 16.20%, nighttime 542.21 minutes, accounting for 40.58%). The average active time is 775.37 minutes, accounting for 56.78% of the total time of 1 day and night, the rest time is 664.63 minutes, accounting for 43.22%. The results of this study contribute to increasing understanding of the species and applying it in effective breeding conditions to conserve this rare animal.

Keywords: *activities, behavior, captivity, civet, morphology.*

Introduction

The palm civet - *Paradoxurus hermaphroditus* (Pallas, 1777) belongs to the family Viverridae, order Carnivora. This animal is distributed in South China, India, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, Indonesia, Philippines, Thailand, Cambodia (Iseborn et al., 2012), Nepal, Singapore (Shepherd, 2012), Sri Lanka, Vietnam and scattered in some other places in the world (Duckworth et al., 2016). This is an omnivorous animal, mainly eating fruits, and plays an important role in seed dispersal in the forest (Joshi et al., 1995, Grassman, 1998, Nakashima and Sukor, 2010). In Vietnam, the palm civet is

widely distributed throughout the country (Dang Huy Huynh et al., 2010).

The civet is a rare animal in group IIB, prioritized for protection and enforcement of the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Wild Fauna and Flora. The hunting and use of civets for many different purposes such as meat, skin, fur, and spices; use in the production of "civet coffee"; on the other hand, habitat loss or fragmentation is depleting this species in the wild (Marcus et al., 2012). Conservation and preservation of genetic resources is one of the urgent, regular and long-term solutions (FAO, 2007). To sustainably preserve genetic resources of livestock breeds,

the exploitation and development of genetic resources is an effective solution (Nguyen Van Duc, 2016). Currently, in Vietnam, civets are being raised to develop the economy and contribute to preserving biodiversity (Nguyen Lan Hung, 2010).

Recently, Nguyen Thi Thu Hien and colleagues have conducted a number of studies on civets in captivity. A systematic study on the biological characteristics (appearance, nutrition, behavior, growth, reproduction) of civets in captivity in Vietnam has been published (Nguyen Thi Thu Hien et al., 2017a,b,c,d,e; Nguyen Thi Thu Hien et al., 2018a). These results provide important data contributing to the improvement of breeding techniques; increasing the efficiency of civet conservation; creating the premise for similar studies on other wild animals in captivity. The physiological and biochemical indices of blood and urine by age group and by sex in civets were published for the first time in Vietnam (Nguyen Thi Thu Hien et al., 2018b). These results are the scientific basis for research, diagnosis and breeding of wild animals. The authors also evaluated changes in reproductive endocrine indices using non-invasive methods to determine the estrus period of civets (Nguyen Thi Thu Hien et al., 2020). The study determined changes in estradiol and progesterone hormones in the feces of civets in the non-pregnant, pregnant and pseudo-pregnant stages. Another study to evaluate the impact of gonadotropins (PMSG, HCG) on changes in estradiol and progesterone, and on the fertility of female civets in captivity was conducted (Nguyen Thi Thu Hien et al., 2020; Nguyen Thi Thu Hien et al., 2021).

However, there have been no comprehensive and systematic studies on the biological characteristics of civets in captivity, providing a scientific basis for the domestication process, perfecting effective breeding techniques, and contributing to the sustainable conservation of the species. Therefore, studying the behavior of civets in captivity is well-founded and very necessary; in order to improve breeding efficiency to both exploit and conserve this rare wild animal species ex-situ.

Materials and Methods

Research Location

Center for Biotechnology Application in Xuan Duong Commune, Cam My District, Dong Nai Province, Vietnam

Cages

The cages are surrounded by sturdy walls; 2.5 m high to prevent the civets from escaping, avoiding direct wind, and limiting light. The cement floor has a slope to help drain urine and water during cleaning. Each cage is 1 x 1 x 1.2 m in size; built with a 0.5 m high brick wall below, and a wire mesh above (in Dong Nai), or completely made of wire mesh (in Thu Duc). Inside the cage, place a plastic basket or ceramic tube for the civets to lie on. When the breeding stage comes, line the basket with soft cloth to make a nest for the civets.

The cages are cleaned with tap water every day. Disinfection is carried out once a month. The disinfectant used is BESTAQUAM-SR. Each cage is marked on the door, so that each individual civet can be monitored throughout the research process.

Food and Water

The main meal is porridge cooked with various ingredients such as fish, organs, chicken heads. The side meals are various fruits; mainly bananas, papaya, watermelon. The civets are fed 2 meals/day and night, including 1 main meal (around 6pm) and 1 side meal (around 11-12pm). The daily ration for each civet weighing 3kg is: metabolizable energy (ME): 450 Kcal, crude protein (CP): 18 gr, Lipid: 3 gr, dry matter (DM) 105 gr. Drinking water is placed in the cage for the civets to drink by themselves. The water bowl is cleaned daily and the water is changed once a day.

The care and feeding of civets follow the procedures outlined in the manual for the care and use of experimental animals in research and teaching.

Research Methods

Select 64 individuals (32 males, 32 females) to monitor their morphology and behavioral

activity indicators. All civets are raised with the same care and nutrition regimen. Monitor, observe and describe the physical characteristics and some adaptive behaviors of civets in captivity.

Set up cameras, observe images from camera data and record each civet in each cage for 7 consecutive days, calculate the average time for each activity. Activities include: movement (walking, standing, jumping, climbing), biting and destroying the cage, eating, drinking, and hygiene (urinating, defecating). Civets lying still and sleeping are considered inactive.

Data Analysis

Statistical parameters were processed by MS-Excel 2020 software. Data was expressed as mean (Mean \pm SD).

Results and Discussion

Morphological Characteristics of Civets in Captivity

In terms of morphology, civets in captivity also have the same characteristics of the species as in the wild. The fur is gray or brown, with black tips; along the back and flanks there are dark brown spots or often form three stripes running along the back from the shoulder to the base of the ear.

Figure 1. Civet (*P. hermaphroditus*) in Captivity

The tail has an unclear or black streak at the base of the tail, the tail tip is usually black, however in some individuals it can be white; the nose, cheeks, ears, lower thighs and four hooves are black; the belly is gray (Duckworth et al., 2016, Dang Huy Huynh et al., 2010). When the civet is young, the black brown stripes are not clear, the fur is coarse. As it grows older, the fur becomes smoother and the dark brown spots become clearer. The face has 2-3 bright spots on the forehead or next to the eyes. These morphological characteristics prove that the species being kept and studied in captivity is *Paradoxurus hermaphroditus*.

Nutritional Characteristics

Regarding nutritional characteristics, we conducted a field survey and fed common palm civets different types of food. Although belonging to the carnivorous order, palm civets are omnivorous. The survey results showed that palm civets can eat many types of fruit. Their favorite fruit is banana. In animal husbandry, food sources can be changed depending on the season. In terms of vegetables, palm civets do not eat raw vegetables but must be processed (cooked with porridge) before they can use them. Thus, in the season when there are no ripe fruits, we can supplement food of plant origin through vegetable porridge. Regarding animal food sources, palm civets especially like to eat meat, fish, and eggs. The survey results showed that palm civets can eat most of the animal-based foods tested such as: meat of all kinds (pork, beef, chicken), fish, eggs, shrimp, crab, snails. Palm civets can eat both raw and cooked meat. However, to ensure the health of civets, it is necessary to cook animal food sources before feeding them. In breeding conditions, to save costs, ensure supply, and at the same time meet the nutritional needs of civets, porridge cooked with chicken heads or rice mixed with cooked ground chicken heads is a suitable and commonly used food. According to Dang Huy Huynh et al. (2010); Duckworth (2016), civets are omnivorous animals, they can eat most of the food that humans eat.

Figure 2. Civet is Eating Coffee Beans

Figure 3. Civet is Eating Watermelon

Activity Behavior

Regarding activity behavior, civets are mainly active at night and sleep during the day. Excretion activities are mainly performed at the beginning of the evening activity phase. Civets have a very high territorial defense behavior. When releasing other civets into the same cage, they will bite each other. Civets only pair up when the female shows signs of estrus. This proves that in captivity, civets still retain the solitary living behavior of the species (Dang Huy Huynh et al., 2010). At night, male civets secrete musk, which can be easily recognized in the cage area, especially during the breeding season.

In captivity, studying the day-night activity behavior of civets is very necessary because through the activities of civets, breeders can predict the health status and control the activities of civets, thereby having a reasonable care and feeding regimen.

The results of observing the day and night activities of 64 common palm civets collected from camera data for 7 consecutive days are presented in Table 1. The activities of the common palm civets observed include: Movement (walking, standing, jumping), eating, sleeping, excreting (defecating, urinating), licking fur, biting the cage, calling, listening and relationships with other Civets.

Table 1. Activity of Civets in Captivity

Time (hour of day)	Rest		Activities	
	Mean (Minute)	Percentage %	Mean (Minute)	Percentage %
5-6	22,12	1,53	37,88	2,63
6-7	47,21	3,28	12,79	0,89
7-8	48,52	3,37	11,48	0,80
8-9	49,29	3,42	10,71	0,75
9-10	49,29	3,42	10,71	0,75
10-11	35,79	2,48	14,21	1,69
11-12	22,87	1,59	27,13	2,58
12-13	49,71	3,45	10,29	0,72
13-14	49,15	3,41	10,85	0,76

14-15	47,89	3,32	12,11	0,85
15-16	29,91	2,07	22,09	2,10
16-17	8,82	0,61	25,18	3,56
17-18	41,78	2,90	18,22	1,27
18-19	39,78	2,76	20,22	1,41
19-20	31,95	2,22	20,05	1,95
20-21	8,97	0,62	51,03	3,55
21-22	8,92	0,62	51,08	3,55
22-23	1,38	0,09	58,62	4,08
23-0	1,10	0,08	58,90	4,09
0-1	0,89	0,06	59,11	4,11
1-2	2,37	0,16	57,63	4,01
2-3	6,98	0,48	53,02	3,69
3-4	8,72	0,60	51,28	3,57
4-5	17,23	1,23	42,77	2,94
Total	664,63	43,22	775,37	56,78

Through table 1, it can be seen that the common palm civets are more or less active at all hours of the day. Day and night activities alternate between activity and rest, the civets rest more during the day than at night.

Based on table 1, it can be divided into 3 phases of activity alternating with 3 rest phases. Activity phase I: from 10-12 am, has an activity time of 41.34 minutes, accounting for 4.27%. In this phase, the most active time is from 11-12 am (27.13 minutes). Activity phase II: from 3-5 pm, has an activity time of 47.27 minutes, accounting for 5.66%. In this phase, the most active time is from 16-17 pm (25.18 minutes). Activity phase III: from 8-5 am, has an activity time of 483.44 minutes, accounting for 33.59%. During this phase, the most active time is from 22-01 (176.63 minutes). Of the three active phases, phase III has the highest activity level and is the main active time of civets, followed by phase II. Common activities occurring during the phases are eating, walking, licking the lips, biting the cage and making calls to their fellows.

Interspersed with the active phases is the resting phase. Resting phase I: from 5-10 am, the resting

time is 194.31 minutes, accounting for 13.49%. Resting phase II: from 12-15 pm, the resting time is 146.75 minutes, accounting for 10.18%. Resting phase III: from 15-19 pm, the active time is 113.51 minutes, accounting for 7.88%. In the 3 resting phases, phase I has the longest resting time due to the intense activity in phase II, followed by phase II and then phase III. In the resting phases, civets mainly sleep. Thus, the results show that the civets are most active at night. Daytime is the time when civets rest the most. The day-night activities of the common palm civet are different, the night-time activity phase is higher than the day-time activity phase. We can see that the next phase of high activity is the high resting phase.

Distribution of Activities and Rest between Day and Night

The data in Table 2 shows that: In a day and night, the common palm civet has more active time than rest time. On average, the active time accounts for 775.37 minutes, accounting for 56.78% of the total time of a day and night, the rest time is 664.63 minutes, accounting for 43.22%.

Table 2. Activity Time Distribution of Civets by Day and Night

Time	Behavior	Mean (Minute) Mean ±SD	Percentage %
Total of Day and night	Activities	775,37 ± 32,54	56,78
	Rest	664,63 ± 31,25	43,22
Day	Activities	233,16 ± 25,32	16,20

	Rest	542,13 ±28,52	37,64
Night	Activities	542,21 ±43,36	40,58
	Rest	122,50 ±28,32	5,58

The time of daytime activity is less than the time of nighttime activity, 233.16 minutes during the day, accounting for 16.20%, and 542.21 minutes at night, accounting for 40.58%. The distribution of activities of the Palm Civet is mainly concentrated at night. The rest period during the day and the activity period at night are equivalent (542.21 minutes of activity, 542.13 minutes of rest). According to Duckworth et al., (2008), Dang Huy Huynh et al., 2010), Palm Civets in the wild are mainly nocturnal. Thus, the day and night activities of Palm Civets in captivity still retain the behavior of the species in the wild. However, in captivity, the activities of Palm Civets are also influenced by humans, the conditions of care and raising of the civets, and the living environment. Therefore, further research is needed on factors affecting the behavior of this species in captivity.

Conclusion

In captivity, the civet is an omnivorous species, with the same morphological and behavioral characteristics as in the wild. The main activities of the civet are moving, eating and resting. Civets are most active at night (daytime 233.16 minutes, accounting for 16.20%, nighttime 542.21 minutes, accounting for 40.58%). On average, the active time accounts for 775.37 minutes, accounting for 56.78% of the total time of 1 day and night, the rest time is 664.63 minutes, accounting for 43.22%. The results of this study contribute to increasing understanding of the species and applying it in effective breeding conditions to conserve this rare animal in ex-situ.

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